

PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPONENTS OF SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF MODERN FEMALE LEADERS

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ABSTRACT

Gender equality is a very important process in our democratic country. Today, the number of women leaders is increasing. The article discusses the psychological components of social adaptation of modern women leaders.

INTRODUCTION The analysis of scientific-theoretical literature shows that a certain basis for the study of the concept of "social adjustment" has been formed today in the fields of science, including philosophy, pedagogy, psychology, law, medicine, and sociology. In fact, the scientific-theoretical study and systematic research of the concept of "social adaptation" is a special research object of national sociology. Man's internal drive for continuous development and the constantly changing social environment are the source of constant adaptation. Socialization and social adaptation are closely related and reflect the unity of individual and collective interaction. "Social adaptation" is the basis of socialization mechanisms, adaptation of a person to a new social environment. The socio-psychological content of social adaptation provides that the purpose of the community's direction, experience, the individual's acquisition of the group's culture, customs, and moral norms are expressed in accordance with it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

E. Durkheim, a classic example of sociology, defines the concept of social adaptation in the dictionary as follows, "social adaptation is the assimilation of social norms by an individual. Adaptation of the individual and adaptation of the society is a qualitatively and quantitatively single process, and the concepts of "adaptation" and "socialization" are synonyms. However, the normative model of society is not ideal. The concept of positivism is interpreted as a necessary, but not sufficient, methodological basis for revealing the theory of social adaptation"[1].

M. Weber pointed out that there is a possibility of having several mutually exclusive norms at the same time [2]. This approach shows the importance of the norm in the formation of the individual and the role of the individual in the formation of the norm. Thus, a relatively adapted person is not "normative", but rather "rational", although a "normative" person is sufficiently "rational". M. Weber points to the primary (perhaps relative) of man, and

the secondary of society, which is very important for our understanding of social adaptation.

T. Parsonc's views on social adaptation are also interesting. His concept of "society in balance" is dedicated to the balance between the needs of the individual and the social environment, which takes place during the acquisition of the important social norms of the individual in this environment. As long as there is balance - society is stable, if there is no balance - social conflict occurs. An important task of society is to strive for this balance, although according to T. Parsonc, absolute balance cannot be achieved. An individual's needs and social norms are dynamic values, and their alignment can happen unexpectedly and only for a short period of time. T. Parsons, using the terms "adaptation" and "social environment", emphasized that a person always interacts not with society as a whole, but with a small part of it [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

What exactly are the advantages of female leaders? We will find the answer to this question. Owners of natural instincts in communication. Today, every field needs skilled communicators, and women are very successful in this regard. Because of their natural communication instincts, women can be more strategic when it comes to managing relationships than men. With these features, women strengthen the organizational culture, increase the reputation of the organization, and ensure the implementation of corporate social responsibility projects.

They set their own standards. When we look at strong female leaders, we see some common traits: successful female leaders set their own standards and fight for them.

Despite the fact that they sometimes face serious criticism, they are able to behave professionally in the struggle for standards. Positive energy is their companion. Women leaders who strive to empower themselves and others bring color to life. Eating well, dressing colorfully, laughing, dancing are characteristic of many women, and these characteristics raise the energy of the organization they lead.

They excel in the fight against stress. Even in a family environment, in many cases, they manage crises and tensions: they anticipate any dangerous signs that may appear in front of family members and take precautionary measures. Women can easily overcome stress through love, balance, sense of danger, constructive approach.

Versatility. They can even worry about their duties at work while talking about their children, motherhood worries, and housework.

In terms of ensuring their versatility, women are more determined than men. Studies show that the percentage of women participating in individual education is 80%. Curious female leaders who ask more questions and seek inspiration through self-management emerge as passionate followers who seek excellence.

Good listeners. By nature, loving female leaders are good listeners. Being a good listener is important in solving problems. Women, who don't always have to have the final say, enjoy working collaboratively by creating ecosystems and generalizing ideas.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the social environment, which changes from time to time, is a source of constant adaptation in the formation of a modern female leader. Adaptation is a continuous, lifelong process

with its own dynamics and relative stability. There are several types of adaptation - production, professional, socio-psychological, cultural, material, political-legal, labor, educational, and so on, which does not give the researcher the opportunity to focus on several types at once, so he cannot choose any particular one. studies the type, which prevents the creation of a holistic picture of human adaptation. Summarizing the advanced theories in science, it is possible to come to the conclusion that social adaptation occurs as a result of a person's active participation in the process of family, neighborhood, education, work activities. A person purposefully modifies adaptive mechanisms or uses them to improve his ability to adapt to the social conditions of his lifestyle. This means that the society not only adapts to one or another changes

under the influence of external and internal conditions, but acquires the ability to adapt a person to society through the system of social institutions, with the help of various forms, mechanisms and carriers of social adaptation. Social adaptation is the process of formation of a person in the system of social relations as a component of this system, that is, a person becomes a part of a social community, a group of people, an organization. In this, the process of assimilation of culture, social norms and values, which serve as a basis for the formation of personal qualities, takes place. For a leading woman, social relations are an environment that fulfills her needs and provides an opportunity to master the main qualities that distinguish her from other people on Earth.

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